

MONITORING AND EVALUATION DIMENSIONS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KENYA: ASSESSMENT OF ITS EFFECT ON IMPLEMENTATION OF STRATEGIC PLANS

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Abstract:

The government of Kenya recognizes the importance of implementing strategic plans in public schools as the key approach of management of institutions, strategic planning is very crucial in realization of management outlook for the Kenyan vision 2030, relatively little research has investigated the ways public schools implement strategic plans. This study was designed to assess the effect of monitoring and evaluation on implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools in Kenya. The study was guided by a mixed method Research design. The target population for the study was 9 sub-county education officials, 284 chairpersons of Board of management, 284 principals and 284 senior teachers in Bungoma County. The study sample comprised of 9 sub-county education officials, 85 chairpersons of Board of management, 85 principals and 85 senior teachers. The respondents were selected using purposive and simple random sampling technique and the instruments for data collection were questionnaires, interview schedule and document analysis. Data was analyzed using mean, standard deviation, frequency, Pearson Correlation Coefficient and Multiple Regression to establish relationships and variable traits while themes were derived from narrative data. The findings of this study revealed that monitoring and evaluation dimension has a significant relationship with implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools. It is recommend that it is very crucial that the public secondary schools conduct monitoring and evaluation on the strategic plans, this will

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help the educational institutions to gather valuable information that will provide valuable insights in the strategic plans implementation across the education sector.

Keywords: monitoring, evaluation, implementation, strategic plans

1. Introduction

A strategic plan has been defined by authors differently in different circumstances. According to Conley (2013), a strategic plan is a plan that includes beliefs, a mission, vision, objectives and strategies in a school. He regards strategic plans as tools that many organizations use to keep themselves successful and on always be on track, a strategic plan is a roadmap for success. You can use the same genus of educational plans to establish a route to academic success in school or college. The plan may involve a strategy for achieving success in a single year of school or for your entire educational experience (Fleming, 2013).

According to Basham and Lunenburg, (2013), strategic planning is a disciplined effort to produce fundamental decisions and actions that shape and guide what an organization is, what it does, and why it does it, with a focus on the future. The real value of strategic plans in a school is more than simply the outcome of having an outline that guides future problem solving and decision making, but it is a powerful and effective way to build consensus and motivate resource support and is particularly useful in defining priorities for the board, the head of school and administrative team who are charged with the implementation of the plan.

The Kenyan Education Sector has since the year 2013 embarked on plans to institute reforms at all levels. The Ministry of education circular; MOE/PLAN POLICY/NO.12/04/2013 instructed that all secondary schools should develop strategic plans and submits copies to the permanent secretary. In view of that, the Kenya's ministry of education demands that adequate and deliberate planning should be made to ensure continuous and phase improvement and provision of all resources that contribute to effective and efficient performance and development.

While the education reforms in Kenya takes place, the role of strategic plans cannot be underscored. Many researchers have carried out studies to establish importance of strategic plans in school development. Romney, (2011), noted that a strategic plan cannot only refocus members' sense of purpose, but can stimulate organizational structure future oriented thinking based on a shared sense of mission and vision. Strategic planning is a meticulous process for creating a map for the general path that the institutions are to follow, with the intention to increase the institutional

potential output. The rapidly dynamic changing information communication technology, economic, political and social trends have created a need for institutions to re-align their goals, objectives and set mandate for their nations to achieve faster development. The new political dispensation requires institutions to re-assess their competitiveness of the service delivery and products, in order for the country to attain a middle level industrialization status. The recognition of knowledge based economy becomes a key mandate, and hence the need to impart appropriate skills to its citizen (Sakorkar, 2013).

According to Government of Kenya, (2011), education is widely recognized as key dimension to national development. An increase in access, retention, equity and quality of education, relative to the national population is critical to social-economic growth and productivity; increase individual earning and subsequently reduced income inequalities and reduction in poverty index, It also contributes significantly to gross National health; enhance democracy, good governance and effective institutional leadership. Since the attainment of political independence in 1963, the government of Kenya has placed major emphasis on the role of education in social-economic and political development. As a result, it has considerably expanded access through opening of more schools. This expansion has not been without major challenges, one of which is educational management.

The EFA 2000 Assessment Report for Kenya indicates that although education has been a concern for the government and other development actors, Kenya is yet to achieve EFA goals given the increasing level of poverty, continued implementation of structural adjustment programmes (SAPs) and servicing of both domestic and international debts. The poor, who contribute 60 percent of the population, continue to miss out on education, notwithstanding the quality of education (Oketch & Rolleston, 2012). In searching for the means to achieve improvement educational leadership and management, the government and educators have looked to the quality techniques developed in business and industry to provide suitable tool to enhance quality education. Thus, strategic planning has been embraced to reverse this situation of deteriorating quality in our public schools education and leadership.

A strategic plan is a document developed to give a school focus and directions as it prepares for the future by continuously adjusting its academic direction. In response to a changing academic landscape, successful educational, economic and planning effort produce many benefits some of which Hellriegel and Slocum (2010) identifies as: first, the promotion of strategic thought and action is based upon data gathered about the institution; systematic information gathering will result as a benefit of strategic planning; secondly, improved organizational decision-making. In strategic planning,

vital issues and challenges must be identified and planned for; and lastly, improved organizational responsiveness and improved performance. Members of the institution will respond positively to an administration that works towards resolution of the issues facing it. Strategic planning helps organization to clarify future direction, to establish priorities, to diversify its products or services and to deal effectively with rapidly changing circumstances.

In this era of globalization where the world has undergone many rapid changes in all fields, the environment in which organizations operate is no longer stable and predictable. Networking dimensions then can provide an operational framework allowing organizations to lead changes and gain their competitive edge in strategic planning implementation (Schraeder, 2012). According to Republic of Kenya (2009) one factor that stands out as a key determinant in achieving quality education is school planning effectiveness. Strategic planning is a line of action designed by the school to achieve desired targets within a scale using available resources. Strategic planning has been used in schools in developed countries, leading to school improvement and advancement in quality education.

In United States of America, strategic planning implementation follows a four step process for planning in a school wide program: by conducting a comprehensive needs assessment; managing the inquiry process, designing the school wide program; and monitoring and evaluating of the program (Cook, 2013). In Europe, there have been major strides made in school development. According to Deal (2014) the education sector is still faced with major challenges that have to be addressed such as interplay between planning education and practice in terms of the experiences of researchers, teachers, professionals and consultants; learning skills and attitudes in planning education and problem solving; role of new technologies in planning education (E-learning, E-tools, E-Networking; place of ethics in planning education, planning education programmes in a selected number of European Union countries and the utility of teaching learning resources.

Oyedepo, (2010) points out that Japan was able to make a drastic transformation and reformation through strategic planning and strategic implementation of its educational sector. It is in view of this that this research study has been provoked, to find out the networking dimensions as determinants of implementation school strategic plans to enhance quality environment for quality education. A recent requirement in education reforms in Kenya demands that education management and the sector as a whole needs to refocus its role so as to achieve its set targets. Hence, there is need for schools to adopt and embrace performance based management for effective attainment of the school objectives. Among the many challenges facing educational institutions is

poor performance and lack of adequate physical and human resources (Education News Magazine of 30th November, 2011).

Republic of Kenya (2011) affirms that the Ministry of education is responsible for providing an appropriate regulatory framework, developing policies and guidelines, providing educational support services, mobilizing resources for education sector inputs, and coordinating human capital development through education and training. Omboi and Mucai, (2011), carried out an analysis of the factors influencing the implementation of strategic plans in selected schools in Meru South District, Kenya and focused on managerial behavior, institutional policies, resources allocation, reward and incentive influence on implementation of strategic plans.

The study findings pointed out that the strategic thinking of the school managers and the extrinsic motivation of the teachers contributed largely to the extent to which the strategies were implemented. Most of the strategic plans are kept in the school principal's office only to be made available during external school inspectors (Omboi & Mucai, 2011). In developing countries, promotion of school development involves assessing the current state of the school development plan and providing information about it, by increasing the overall rate of development by carrying out special programs and trying to improve co-ordination between different stages of planning process. The main problem is in the implementation of these strategic plans (Lawrence, 2015).

Cummingham (2011) defines strategic planning as a disciplined effort to produce fundamental decisions and actions that shape and guide what an organization is, what it does and why it does it. To deliver the best results, strategic planning requires broad yet effective information gathering, development and exploration of strategic alternative, and an emphasis on future implications of present decisions. The foregoing authors (Hellriegel & Slocum 2011; Romney, 2011) consent that strategic planning involves a process of charting the way of the future in consideration of the present and the means to get to the desired future.

Canole (2013) conducted a study on strategic planning in three different school districts in United States of America and found that strategic planning had several benefits. One of the major benefits was the change in the way people perform. The find showed that strategic planning process involved the entire community; it was a much more democratic way of planning for the district, the study also revealed that school strategic thinking and acting emanate from strategic planning. Lane, Bishop and Jones. (2010), also point out that strategic planning in education has several benefits a strategic plan establishes a vision, mission, and beliefs for the school district; the plan establishes the path to accomplish its desired future; the plan provides for a path which allows the community to work together to accomplish these goals, objectives, and activities that

constitute the strategic plan; it allows for an understanding of how a school district works, how finances are spent, and identifies the needs of the school district; and allows the school district to set a specific data-driven priorities.

The above studies on strategic planning pointed out the many possible benefits of strategic planning. However, they all noted that it is a complex process that requires leadership to ensure that it is carried out effectively. The Principal as a chief executive plays a critical role in this engagement. The Principal is required to come up with plan strategies which are geared towards incorporating all stakeholders in the school. Results of the research done by Ralph (2008) concluded that the intensity with which education institutions engage in the use of formal strategic planning has a direct positive effect on schools' general development and mediates the effect of managerial and organizational factors on school's overall performance. The results also indicated a reciprocal relationship between strategic planning intensity and performance. That is, strategic plans intensity causes better performance and in turn, better performance causes greater strategic planning intensity (Ralph, 2008).

Strategic planning emerged in public education as a management tool in the mid-20s. The term appeared in educational publications for the first time around 1974, and by 2000 an estimated five hundred school districts around United States of America were using some type of strategic planning (Conley, 2012). Kaufman and Herman (2011) present a clear picture of the process of strategic planning from start to the end. This process includes selecting desired results, identifying a mission, assessing school needs in order to formulate new purposes, developing and implementing action plans, and monitoring and evaluating the success of the strategic plans. Kaufman and Herman (2011) support this and suggest similar practical guidelines, concrete techniques and pragmatic advice geared explicitly to educational practitioners.

In Kenya school, planning involves determining society and student needs, prioritizing school needs, preparing action plans, implementing and monitoring the plans (School Management Guide, 2009). In order to justify their existence schools need to develop strategies that embrace changes by anticipating challenges sufficiently in advance and by planning timely response, increasing speed of implementing of response, being flexible and respond on time to surprises which could not be anticipated in advance. Schools guided by the national goals of education must set up specific objectives designed at helping every individual student achieve varied aspirations and hence develop society. According to the Kenya Education Master Plan for Education and Training (2008–2012) an education strategic plan should contain all important information about the school. This information includes the school aims which should be related to the national goals, school mission statement, description of

school and the community it serves, school priorities, action plan for the next 3years, and information about the school community. Government of Kenya (2011) outlined the major determinant of quality education as curriculum content, relevant instructional material and equipment, physical facilities, ideal learning environment, the quality of teaching force, assessment and monitoring of learning achievement.

Networking dimensions is essential for education institutions to achieve both short term and long term objectives. School principals and senior management's beliefs, values and assumptions are important to the overall success of their envisaged agenda, since the role of leadership in management is largely determined by the culture of the school. School leadership is therefore focused on senior management. Strategic planning is a technique one can use to create an outline or path for long term direction so as to achieve a favourable future and help an institution to prosper through institution's stakeholders' participation. It is important to effectively communicate the vision as the strategic soundness of the journey for which school management has opted (Thompson, Strickland & Gamble, 2010).

1.1 Statement of the Problem

In 2011, the Government of Kenya through the Ministry of Education embarked on a process of implementing the provisions of the Constitution of Kenya 2010 that required decentralization of Education provision to the County government level through a programme named Decentralized Education Management Activity (DEMA). To this end, the approach uses the concepts of "Strategic Planning" and "Performance-Based Management in capacity building for Secondary Public schools in Kenya. However studies have found that majority of schools have therefore developed their own strategic plans depending on their status, needs and objectives, but most of the strategic plans are kept in the school principal's office, only to be made available during external school inspection visit. It was against this background that the researcher was motivated to explore existing monitoring and evaluation dimensions utilized and examined alternative monitoring and evaluation dimensions for implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools in Bungoma County, Kenya.

1.2 Objective of the Study

1. To establish existing monitoring and evaluation dimensions utilized by schools for Implementation of Strategic Plans.
2. To examine alternative monitoring and evaluation dimensions for Implementation of Strategic Plans.

1.3 Hypothesis of the Study

Ho: There is no statistically significant relationship between monitoring and evaluation dimensions and implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools.

2. Research Methodology and Methods

The study adopted the pragmatism research paradigm. Pragmatism is a deconstructive paradigm that advocates the use of mixed methods in research, “sidesteps the contentious issues of truth and reality in collecting and analyzing data. Research methodology describes the overall approach to research design, Creswell and Plano (2011) are of the view that methodology is a strategy or a plan of action that links methods to outcomes and governs the choice and use of methods. A research methodology forms the overall paradigm/approach that shapes research approach to the study. In this study, the researcher used a mixed approach. In this study, the researcher has the positivist assumption of a fixed, measurable reality external to people. In mixed methods studies, researchers purposely integrate quantitative and qualitative data rather than keeping them separate so as to maximize the strengths and minimize the weakness of each type of methodology. A mixed methods designs involves the collection and analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data in a single study in which data are collected concurrently or sequentially, then they are given priority, and involve integration of the data at one or more stages in the process of research (Onwuegbuzie & Collins, 2007). This study adopted a concurrent approach where both quantitative and qualitative data was collected at the same time and using the same research study respondents. It mixed both quantitative and qualitative research instruments by use of triangulation to get contrast. This study used the interview schedule and Questionnaires to collect data. The study found it necessary to use the instruments in order to achieve the stated objectives besides the combination of all the instruments was meant to capture both quantitative and qualitative data (Kothari, 2008).

Interview and questionnaires were used to get information monitoring and evaluation dimensions implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools. The researcher utilized these tools to eliminate subjective bias and get an in depth view of the problem. This data collection instrument was used mainly to review the existing effect of monitoring and evaluation dimensions on implementation of strategic plans in public Secondary Schools in Kenya

3. Findings and Discussion

The first objective sought to establish existing monitoring and evaluation dimensions utilized by schools for Implementation of Strategic Plans. The findings are presented below.

3.1 Existing monitoring and evaluation dimensions utilized in Implementation of Strategic Plans

Findings revealed that majority of the respondents were of the opinion that in-service training should be undertaken by stakeholders in public secondary schools on strategic planning. This implies that through good training and development of human resource become viable to implement strategic plans. One of the sub county education officers commented that;

“When head of departments are effectively trained on monitoring and evaluation of implementation of strategic plans, they will facilitate a proper strategic plans implementation practice in public secondary schools, since they are normally given the duties to monitor and evaluation of the whole exercise by the school principals thus training should be vital so as to ensure effective strategic plans implementation”

They therefore have to undergo some training and guidance on the development and use of strategic plans. Similarly, those principals with some planning and reporting experience to help them evaluate and further develop a school's related processes and systems often use planning in their day to day running of the school.

Experienced principals take planning and reporting beyond being an exercise in compliance. It makes them to appreciate the contribution that improving student learning throughout the school can make their effectiveness as a school leader as narrated by the respondents;

“Each school’s context and needs differ. Principals may be at a different point of capability in the planning and reporting process; some may be new in the headship while others may lack the knowledge in strategic plan development and strategic plans implementation.”

Since previously many teacher training colleges and universities have not been offering courses and training on strategic planning then most new principals may find difficulties in the use of the strategic plans.

3.2 Alternative monitoring and evaluation dimensions for Implementation of Strategic Plans

In view to assess the effect of monitoring and evaluation on implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools in Kenya, the second objective sought to examine alternative monitoring and evaluation dimensions for implementation of Strategic Plans. The findings are represented in table 1.

Table 1: Alternative monitoring & evaluation on Implementation Strategic Plans

Statements			SD	D	U	A	SA	TOTAL	MEAN	SD
Our school specifies measurement & evaluation schedules for strategic plans	F	0	0	2	204	132	336	4.38	0.507	
	%	0	0	1.1	60.1	38.8	100	87.6		
The surplus resource on non-critical activities can be diverted to critical activities thus reducing the duration over which the project can be done	F	0	0	1	184	141	336	4.44	0.504	
	%	0	0	0.4	55.4	44.2	100	88.8		
Supervision and control should be enhanced on strategic plan implementation to see if it is in the right course	F	0	0	1	162	163	336	4.51	0.508	
	%	0	0	0.4	48.2	51.4	100	90.2		
The quality assurance and standards officers from the ministry of education should supervise strategic plan policy in public secondary schools	F	0	0	1	336	166	336	4.49	0.508	
	%	0	0	0.4	50.0	49.6	100	89.8		
In-service training should be undertaken by stakeholders in public secondary schools on strategic planning	F	0	0	2	155	89	336	4.52	0.522	
	%	0	0	1.1	46.0	52.9	100	90.4		
There is operational development of timelines and schedules in our strategic plan implementation	F	0	0	2	166	168	336	4.49	0.522	
	%	0	0	1.1	48.9	50.0	100	89.8		
Our school modifies the strategic plan and redesign processes as needed in response to analysis of school needs a raise	F	0	0	1	173	162	336	4.47	0.507	

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		%	0	0	0.4	51.8	47.8	100	89.4
Our school establishes consensus among stakeholders on specific indications on monitoring and evaluation purposes	F	0	0	2	184	120	336	4.43	0.511
		%	0	0	0.7	55.4	43.8	100	88.6

Key: SD=1, D=2, U=3, A=4, SA=5, %=Percentage, F=frequency, S Dev=Standard Deviation

The study findings indicated that 1.1% were undecided that their school specifies measurement and evaluation schedules for strategic plans, 60.1% agreed that their school specifies measurement and evaluation schedules for strategic plans while 38.8% strongly agreed that their school specifies measurement & evaluation schedules for strategic plans. The study results revealed that 87.6% (mean=4.38) were of the view that their school specifies measurement and evaluation schedules for strategic plans. The findings agree with Ralph, (2008) that principals who are new to planning and reporting could not adequately embrace use of strategic planning. They therefore have to undergo some training and guidance on the development and use of strategic plans. Similarly, those principals with some planning and reporting experience to help them evaluate and further develop a school's related processes and systems often use planning in their day to day running of the school.

The study findings indicated that 0.4% were undecided that the surplus resource on non-critical activities can be diverted to critical activities thus reducing the duration over which the project can be done, 55.4% agreed that the surplus resource on non-critical activities can be diverted to critical activities thus reducing the duration over which the project can be done while 44.2% strongly agreed that the surplus resource on non-critical activities can be diverted to critical activities thus reducing the duration over which the project can be done. 88.8% (mean=4.44) were of the opinion that the surplus resource on non-critical activities can be diverted to critical activities thus reducing the duration over which the project can be done.

The study findings indicated that 0.4% were undecided that supervision and control should be enhanced on strategic plan implementation to see if it is in the right course, 48.2% agreed that supervision and control should be enhanced on strategic plan implementation to see if it is in the right course while 51.4% strongly agreed that supervision and control should be enhanced on strategic plan implementation to see if it is in the right course. 90.2% (mean=4.51) were of the opinion that supervision and control should be enhanced on strategic plan implementation to see if it is in the right course.

The study findings indicated that 0.4% were undecided that in-service training should be undertaken by stakeholders in public secondary schools on strategic planning, 50.0% agreed that in-service training should be undertaken by stakeholders in public secondary schools on strategic planning while 49.6% strongly agreed that in-service training should be undertaken by stakeholders in public secondary schools on strategic planning. 90.4% (mean=4.51) were of the opinion that in-service training should be undertaken by stakeholders in public secondary schools on strategic planning.

The study findings indicated that 1.1% were undecided that there is operational development of timelines and schedules in our strategic plan implementation, 46.0% agreed that there is operational development of timelines and schedules in our strategic plan implementation while 52.9% strongly agreed that there is operational development of timelines and schedules in our strategic plan implementation. The study further revealed that 89.8% (mean=4.49) were of the view that there is operational development of timelines and schedules in our strategic plan implementation. The findings are in tandem with studies by Kaufman and Herman (2011) which revealed that a clear picture of the process of strategic planning from start to the end includes selecting desired results, identifying a mission, assessing school needs in order to formulate new purposes, developing and implementing action plans, and monitoring and evaluating the success of the strategic plans.

The study findings indicated that 0.4% were undecided that their school modifies the strategic plan and redesign processes as needed in response to analysis of school needs a raise, 51.8% agreed that their school modifies the strategic plan and redesign processes as needed in response to analysis of school needs a raise while 47.8% strongly agreed that their school modifies the strategic plan and redesign processes as needed in response to analysis of school needs a raise. 89.4% (mean=4.47) were of the opinion that their school modifies the strategic plan and redesign processes as needed in response to analysis of school needs a raise.

The study findings indicated that 0.7% were undecided that their school establishes consensus among stakeholders on specific indications on monitoring and evaluation purposes, 55.4% agreed that their school establishes consensus among stakeholders on specific indications on monitoring and evaluation purposes while 43.8% strongly agreed that their school establishes consensus among stakeholders on specific indications on monitoring and evaluation purposes. 88.6% (mean=4.43) were of the opinion that their school establishes consensus among stakeholders on specific indications on monitoring and evaluation purposes.

The study results revealed that majority of the respondents were of the opinion that in-service training should be undertaken by stakeholders in public secondary schools on strategic planning. This implies that through good training and development of human resource become viable to implement strategic plans.

3.3 Significant Relationship between Monitoring & Evaluation Dimensions and Implementation of Strategic Plans

The hypothesis of the study sought to find out whether there was significant relationship between monitoring and evaluation dimensions and implementation of strategic plans. To answer this, a hypothesis was set:

Ho: There is no statistically significant relationship between monitoring and evaluation dimensions and implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools.

To establish if there was any correlation between monitoring and evaluation dimensions and evaluation dimensions and implementation of strategic plans, Pearson's product moment correlation was carried out. Table 2.

Table 2: Relationship between M&E and Implementation of Strategic plans

Correlations		Implementation of S. Plans	M&E
Implementation of strategic plans	Pearson Correlation	1	.649**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	336	336
M & E	Pearson Correlation	.649**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	336	336

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 shows that there was a significant relationship between monitoring and evaluation systems and implementation of strategic plan in public secondary schools ($r=0.649$, $p=0.000$). Comparing this value p value with alpha, in this case 0.000; since the "sig." level is less than alpha, the results are significant. Therefore, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis that there is no statistically significant relationship between monitoring and evaluation systems and implementation of strategic plan in public secondary schools. The alternate hypothesis there is a statistically significant relationship between monitoring and evaluation systems and implementation of strategic plan in public secondary schools was accepted. This implies that there was a significant relationship between monitoring and evaluation systems and implementation of strategic plan in public secondary schools in Bungoma County.

The positive nature of the relationship between monitoring and evaluation systems and implementation of strategic plan in public secondary schools implies that change in monitoring and evaluation systems leads to an increase in the implementation of strategic plan in public secondary schools in Bungoma County. These findings corroborate those of Adanusa, (2012) that indicated that lack of measurement and evaluation of plans in school is a challenge in strategic plan implementation. Evaluations need to be undertaken by individuals with the relevant skills, sound methods and adequate resources as well as transparency in order to secure their quality (Jones et al, 2012). This implies the need for the personnel to be highly trained in order to secure the effectiveness of monitoring and evaluation. Further, budgetary allocation is required to provide adequate resources for the evaluation.

4. Conclusion

For effective monitoring and evaluation of implementing strategic plans, school managers should be effectively trained on implementation of strategic plans to facilitate a proper strategic plans implementation practice in public secondary schools since they are normally given the duties to monitor the whole exercise by the school heads thus training is vital to ensure effective strategic plans implementation. The study also recommends that it is very crucial that the public secondary schools conduct monitoring and evaluation on the strategic plans, this will help the institutions to gather valuable information that will provide valuable insights in the strategy implementation. The study recommends that school management monitoring as well as re-assessing the effect of the strategic plan adopted, this will help to identify whether the adopted counteractive measures are making any acceptable difference.

5. Policy Implication

The policy makers would find this study useful in formulating and developing competencies that would enable the schools to improve on strategic planning process and also in addressing the critical issues that may be affecting secondary school education. Therefore, this will help the education fraternity to improve on their strategic plan implementation and generally the way of operations. The findings may also be used as a source of reference for other researchers. In addition, academic researchers need the study findings to stimulate further research in this area. Therefore, this study will form a basis of good educational background for further researches and

extension strategic plan development across the education sector as envisaged in the policy framework.

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